

FRACTURE OF SiC/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Discontinuous SiC/Al composites were fabricated with different size SiC particles in order to study the role of particle size on the fracture process. Tensile test data shows that the Young's modulus is independent of SiC particle size, whereas yield stress and ultimate strength decreases, and strain to fracture and ductility increases as SiC particle size increases. The fracture behavior of SiC/Al is unique in the sense that it has features of brittle and ductile mechanisms. The fracture process is matrix controlled up to SiC particle sizes of 20 μm and above where fracture of SiC begins to dominate. The matrix is influenced by residual hydrostatic tension and high density of dislocations generated at SiC/Al interfaces due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between SiC and Al matrix. Crack initiation fracture toughness does not depend on SiC particle size. Crack growth fracture toughness increases as the size of the SiC particles increase.

INTRODUCTION

Low ductility and fracture toughness of discontinuous SiC/Al composites remains a major obstacle to the practical application of these materials. Despite the significant improvement in the processing of SiC/Al composites in the recent years, fracture toughness is still in the range of 12 to 20 $\text{MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$ [1,2,3]. It is not clear how the interfacial SiC/Al bond strength, difference in CTE between SiC and Al, size of the SiC reinforcement affect the toughness. It has already been established that the increase in the volume fraction of SiC particles and/or whiskers and the increase of the matrix strength influence adversely the toughness of SiC/Al composites [3,4]. This paper will examine the dependence of the toughness and tensile properties of the SiC/Al composites containing various sizes of SiC particles.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

SiC particles of 2.4, 3.2, 8 and 20 μm average size were mixed separately with 1100 Al powder and hot pressed, extruded and hot rolled to produce tensile test samples and compact tension specimens (CTS). Also a SiC/Al composite containing 250 μm size SiC particles was purchased from DWA. The volume fraction of the SiC reinforcement was constant in all composites and equal to 20 volume percent. An 1100 Al alloy was selected in order to minimize the influence of the alloying elements which would otherwise introduce additional complicating factors. Tensile samples were machined in the rolling direction and tested at a standard crosshead speed of 0.05 cm/min. The CTS were machined and tested using single specimen J-integral testing technique in accordance with ASTM E813 standard [5]. All samples were tested in the annealed condition. Also, the energy separation technique, developed at the University of Maryland [6] was utilized as a supplemental method of analyzing load-unload records to increase the confidence in the data obtained. The later technique implies that the area under the load versus displacement curve, which corresponds to the work done by external load, can be separated into the stored elastic strain (potential) energy, U_s , the elastic energy, U_e , released during crack extension, and the plastic energy, U_p , dissipated during crack extension as shown on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the energy separation principle between two successive unloadings.

The rate of the plastic energy dissipation $I = 1/B_N dU_p/da$ and the elastic energy release rate $G = 1/B_N dU_e/da$ represent the plastic and elastic parts of the J-integral, i.e., $J = I + G$, where B_N is the thickness of the CTS between the side grooves and a is the crack length. Crack initiation fracture toughness can be determined as $K_{IC} = (GE_c/1 - \nu^2)^{1/2}$ [7], where E_c is the composite Young's modulus and ν is the Poisson's ratio ($\nu = 0.31$). Also, a direct evaluation of K_{IQ} is possible by taking maximum load P_m from the load-unload record and substituting into the expression $K_{IQ} = P_m/B_N(w)^{1/2} f(a/w)$ [7], where w is the width of the CTS and values of $f(a/w)$ are readily available. Crack growth fracture toughness is evaluated by dimensionless tearing modulus T which is equal to [7,8]: $T = E_c/\sigma_y^2 dJ/da$, where σ_y is the composite yield stress and dJ/da is the slope of the stable crack extension portion of the J versus a plot constructed in accordance with ASTM E813. Crack extension was determined using unloading compliance technique [5,7]. In order to verify the

calculated crack extension values, the tested CTS were exposed to elevated temperature and then fractured. Physical crack lengths are within 5 to 10% from the values calculated by compliance technique.

The interaction between the fracture path and SiC particles is analyzed by counting the number of SiC particles along a random path (RP), and the fracture path (FP) and comparing SiC particle densities and size distributions. Particle size is represented by the longest dimension of the SiC particle. Random path particle count (RPPC) is performed by counting the particles along the perpendicular lines forming a square mesh which is placed on the micrographs of the metallographically polished cross sections of SiC/Al composites. Fracture path particle count (FPPC) is done by incorporating the SiC particles touching both matching sides of the crack on the cross sections of the tested but not separated CTS. In addition, the number of SiC particles fractured by the crack path can be reasonably estimated since both matching halves of the same crack are present on the micrograph. The latter can be used to determine the percent of SiC particles fractured by the crack path using the ratio of,

$$\frac{\# \text{ of particles fractured by crack path}}{\text{FPPC}} .$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Tests

The Young's modulus of the tested SiC/Al composites does not change as a function of SiC particle size and remains constant ~ 89.7 GPa. This agrees quite well with the classical treatment of the composites where Young's modulus E_c is the function of the volume fraction of the reinforcement [4,9]. Constancy of the modulus indicates good reproducibility during the manufacturing process of SiC/Al composites with various SiC particle sizes in terms of the bonding between SiC/Al. The yield stress and ultimate tensile strength decrease as the size of SiC particles increases. This is consistent with the experimental data collected by various investigators [10]. A recent model of the composite strengthening based on dislocation generation due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between SiC and Al [11] is in accord with the data obtained in the current investigation. Uniform strains to the point of instability remain within 6 to 7% range independent of the SiC particle size. This fact suggests that: i) there is no large scale "bulk" yielding in the composites and deformation takes place within a narrow band surrounding the fracture path (thus the observation of possible difference in strain to ultimate load between SiC/Al tensile samples is rather difficult), which correlates quite well with the previous observations in SiC/6061 Al composites [3,12], ii) the difference in the total amount of plastic deformation to fracture between the composite samples containing various sizes of the SiC particles comes mainly at the expense of the deformation taking place during the necking, i.e., plastically unstable portion of the tensile test.

SiC Particle Analysis

The experimental data show that the ratio of SiC particle densities measured along RP and FP does not depend on the SiC particle size, i.e., $RPPC/FPPC = \text{constant} = 0.75$ for 2.4, 3.2, 8 and 20 μm average SiC size

composites. This means that one finds more SiC particles along FP than along any other direction. Thus crack path is attracted towards the SiC particles. The significance of the specific value of 0.75 is not understood. Attraction of the crack front by the second phase particles is discussed elsewhere [13]. The attraction or deflection is determined by the sign of the residual stresses. In case of a tensile residual stress the crack front is attracted towards the particles [13]. The residual hydrostatic tension was reported to exist in SiC/Al composites due to the difference in CTE [14]. The influence of the residual stresses on the fracture path morphology in two phase system was treated theoretically using computer modeling [15]. Considering various levels of hydrostatic tension superimposed on the random arrangement of voids it was shown that the higher residual tension resulted in the lower strain to fracture. Also fracture propagated along the path which had the smallest fracture strain. The percent of SiC particles fractured by the crack path remains around 8% for 2.4, 3.2 and 8 μm average SiC particle size composites and increases to $\sim 25\%$ for 20 μm SiC/Al composite. This result can be treated on the basis of the critical flaw size used in the Griffith fracture mechanics. The probability of finding a critical flaw size in small SiC particle is less than in the coarse one [16].

Fractography

The results of the fracture surface observation can be divided into three groups: 1) fracture surfaces have a dimple morphology, 2) there are two dimple populations: the first, which is associated with SiC particles, and increases its size as the size of the SiC particles increases, and second type consisting of very small dimples located in the space between the SiC related dimples, 3) no indication of fracture of SiC in the case of small SiC sizes ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Fracture surface of 3.2 μm average size SiC/Al composite.

When the SiC size increases the fracture of the particles becomes more apparent. The shape of the dimples is rather equiaxial and there is no

difference in the appearance between fracture surfaces of the tensile and CT specimens. Despite the correlation between the coarse dimples and SiC particles on the fracture surfaces of SiC/Al composites, not all the SiC particles are completely exposed. This corresponds to the earlier observations of the fracture surfaces of SiC/Al composites [2,12], and indicates good bonding between SiC and Al matrix.

Metallography

Observation of the polished cross sections of the tested tensile and CTS does not reveal the presence of the voids below the fracture path (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Polished cross section of 20 μm average size SiC/Al composite tested tensile sample.

This means that fracture process is confined to an extremely narrow band and there is no apparent damage zone adjacent to the fracture surface which generally exists in the classical void nucleation and growth type ductile fracture. Also, very little pull out of the SiC particles from the Al matrix can be found which is indicative of a good SiC/Al interfacial bonding. No voids can be seen in the vicinity and ahead of the crack tip. Instead, a series of short cracks can be seen in the matrix in front of the continuous crack as shown on Fig. 4. Apparently this cracking takes place in the matrix ahead of the crack tip and forms some sort of the damage zone. This primary cracking can be observed as far as $\approx 50 \mu\text{m}$ away from the crack tip for the fine SiC particle (2.4 and 3.2 μm average size) SiC/Al composite and about 110 to 150 μm for the coarse SiC particle size (8 and 20 μm) composites. It is believed that crack propagation occurs by connecting these discontinuous microcracks. It seems that the short microcracks are associated with the clusters of SiC particles (see Fig. 4). Even though the distribution of the SiC particles is predominately homogeneous, on the microscale there are islands of high and low density of SiC particles. The clusters of the inclusions are considered to be a sites

Fig. 4. Cross section through the tested 8 μm average size SiC/Al composite CTS showing the area around the crack tip.

where the damage level reaches extreme values causing the fracture of the entire system [17]. The degree of plastic constraint within the clusters could be much higher than in the rest of the matrix as a result of: i) residual hydrostatic tension and high dislocation density due to the difference in CTE [11,14], and ii) increase of hydrostatic tension during the deformation due to the plastic constraint in the matrix between the particles. These factors make SiC clusters quite favorable for crack initiation. A necessary condition for crack initiation is that the strain energy U stored at the inclusion is sufficient to provide the surface energy S of the newly formed crack surfaces, or $U > S$. The critical stress for crack nucleation can be obtained from the expression [18]:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{E_c \gamma}{d} \right)^{1/2},$$

where σ is the applied uniaxial stress, q is the average stress concentration factor at the inclusion, γ is the specific surface energy of the crack, E_c is the composite Young's modulus and d is the particle size. The location of the crack formation depends on the relative values of γ and q within the inclusion, at the interface or within the matrix [18]. It seems that stress concentration factor q would be quite high between closely spaced particles which is not inconsistent with our observation of the crack formation within the SiC particle clusters.

The very sharp appearance of the crack tip (see Fig. 4) shows that crack blunting between subsequent crack extensions is quite limited. The estimate of the width of the blunted crack δ based on void nucleation and growth model [19] predicts the blunting of about $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ for $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ average size SiC/Al composite. This is much higher than the separation (1 to 2 μm) observed between the matching sides of the crack in CTS machined from SiC/Al composite containing $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ average size SiC particles. Thus the classical void nucleation and growth mechanism of ductile fracture does not give satisfactory description of the crack propagation in SiC/Al composites.

Fracture Initiation Toughness

Crack initiation fracture toughness measured as K_{IC} and K_{IQ} is plotted as a function of the average SiC particle size and is shown on Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Crack initiation fracture toughness of SiC/Al composites measured as K_{IC} (a) and K_{IQ} (b).

The fact that both of these values show the same trend, i.e., no dependence on the size of the SiC particles increases the confidence in the results obtained and supports the energy separation method as a new and powerful tool. The numerical difference ($K_{IC} \approx 18 \text{ MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$ and $K_{IQ} \approx 23 \text{ MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$) between the values of K_{IC} and K_{IQ} can be explained as follows. A finite notch with a root radius of $\approx 150 \mu\text{m}$ was machined in CTS in order to start the crack (as opposed to ASTM E399 requirement of a pre-fatigued crack starter resulting in a geometrically sharp crack). Thus it is reasonable to expect higher values of K_{IQ} which are obtained in accordance with ASTM E399. Using the result of the study of the influence of notch acuity on the fracture initiation toughness [3] in SiC/Al composites we may write

$$K_{IQ} = K_{IC}(r) = K_{IC} \frac{(1 + r/2c)^{3/2}}{(1 + r/c)} ;$$

where $K_{IC}(r)$ is the initiation toughness of the notch with radius r , K_{IC} is the toughness of geometrically sharp crack and c is the adjustable constant related to the microstructure. Substituting values for $K_{IC}(r) = 23 \text{ MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$, $K_{IC} = 18 \text{ MPa} \cdot \sqrt{\text{m}}$ and $r \approx 150 \mu\text{m}$ we obtain value for $c = 20 \mu\text{m}$. It is rather comparable with the size of the fracture process zone observed in $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ average SiC particle size composite. Initiation fracture toughness for $250 \mu\text{m}$ SiC/Al composite is almost by the factor of 2 less than for the

rest of the tested composites. This is apparently due to the premature cracking of 250 μm size SiC particles.

Crack Growth Toughness

Crack growth toughness measured as tearing modulus, T, and plastic part, I, of J-integral is plotted versus the average size of SiC particles in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Crack growth fracture toughness of SiC/Al composites measured as I (a) and T (b).

The increase of the crack growth toughness with an increase of the SiC particle size means that more energy is dissipated during crack extension in the composite with a larger size of SiC particles. As tensile test data shows the yield stress of the SiC/Al composites drops with the increase of the SiC particle size. The same behavior was reported in literature for various alloys containing second phase particles [10]. The size of the plastic zone is inversely proportional to the square of the yield stress [20]. Thus as the size of SiC particles increase, the size of the plastic zone also increases resulting in the increase of dissipated plastic energy which in turn increases the crack growth fracture toughness.

Conclusions

From the data obtained, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Fracture behavior of SiC/Al composites is quite unique and features of both brittle (limited crack blunting, microcracking in front of the crack tip, confinement of the fracture process to a very narrow band) and ductile (dimple morphology of the fracture surface) mechanisms.
2. Fracture process is matrix controlled up to very large particle sizes ($> 20 \mu\text{m}$) and strongly influenced by: i) residual hydrostatic tension and hydrostatic tension due to inhomogeneous plastic deformation, ii) high dislocation density in the regions adjacent to the SiC particles, and iii) local fluctuations in distribution of SiC particles.
3. Crack initiation fracture toughness K_{IC} is independent of the SiC particle size up to very coarse grit sizes when SiC particle fracture takes over.
4. Low values of the crack initiation toughness can be related to a high dislocation density and residual hydrostatic tension due to the difference in CTE between SiC and Al.
5. Young's modulus is not a function of the SiC particle size at a given volume fraction.
6. Yield stress and ultimate strength of the SiC/Al composite decreases as SiC grit size increases.
7. SiC/Al interfacial bond strength is quite high.
8. Crack growth fracture toughness measured by T (tearing modulus) and I (dissipation rate of the plastic energy) increases with the increase of SiC particle size.
9. Increase in the initiation fracture toughness can be expected only when the plastic constraint of the matrix is decreased. This can be achieved by tailoring SiC/Al interfaces to control the interfacial bond strength. By lowering the bond strength the dislocation density could be reduced. This however will result in the decrease of yield stress.

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REFERENCES

1. Divecha, A. P., Fishman, S. G., and Karmarkar, S. D., J. of Metals, 1981, 9, 12.

2. Logsdon, W. A. and Liaw, P. K., Tensile, Fracture Toughness and Fatigue Crack Growth Rate Properties of SiC Whisker and Particulate Reinforced Al Metal Matrix Composites, Westinghouse Scientific Paper 83-1D3-NODEM-P1, December 1983.
3. Crowe, C. R., Gray, R. A., and Hasson, D. F., Proceedings of ICCM-5, ed. by W. Harrigan, San Diego, 1985, p.
4. McDanel, D. L., Met. Trans. A, 1985, 16, 1105.
5. ASTM Standards, Section 3, Vol. 03.01, E813 (1986).
6. Mecklenburg, M. F., Joyce, J. A., Albrecht, P., "Separation of Energies in Elastic-Plastic Fracture", presented at the Third International Symposium on Nonlinear Fracture Mechanics, ASTM, October 1986, Knoxville, Tenn.
7. Latzo, D. G. H., Turner, C. E., Landes, J. D., McCabe, D. E., and Hellen, T. K., Post Yield Fracture Mechanics, 2nd Ed., Elsevier Pub., NY, 1984.
8. Richie, R. O. and Thompson, A. W., Met. Trans. A, 1985, 16, 233.
9. Mogford, I. L., Metallurgical Reviews, 1967, 114, 12, 49-65.
10. Schoutens, J. E., Introduction to Metal Matrix Composite Materials, MMCIAC, 3rd ed., 1982.
11. Arsenault, R. J. and Shi, N., Mat. Sci. & Eng., 1986, 81, 175-87.
12. Nieh, T. G., Rainen, R. A., and Chellman, D. J., Proceedings of ICCM-5, ed. by W. Harrigan, San Diego, 1985, p. 825.
13. Faber, K. T. and Evans, A. G., Acta Met., 1983, 31, 565.
14. Arsenault, R. J. and Taya, M., The Effects of Differences in Thermal Coefficients of Expansion in SiC Whisker 6061 Aluminum Composites, in the Proceedings of a ICCM-5, ed. by W. Harrigan, San Diego, 1985, p. 21. Also accepted for publication in Acta Met.
15. Melander, A., Mat. Sci. and Eng., 1979, 39, 57-63.
16. Davidge, R. W., Mechanical Behavior of Ceramics, Cambridge University Press, 1980.
17. Embury, J. D. and Burger, G., The Role of Microstructure in the Fracture of Structural Steels, in the Proceedings of a Conference on "Inclusions and Residuals in Steels: Effects on Fabrication and Service Behavior", Ottawa, March, 1985.
18. Gurland, J. and Plateau, J., Trans. ASM, 1963, 56, 442.
19. McMeeking, R. M., J. Mech. Physics Solids, 1977, 29, 337.
20. Thomason, P. F., Int. Journ. of Fracture Mech., 1971, 7, 409-419.